

TOWARDS NET ZERO IN THE EUROPEAN ACADEMIES

SUMMARY

Moving to Net Zero is crucial to mitigate the impacts of climate change and preserve a sustainable future for generations to come. European academies of sciences and humanities play a vital role by providing authoritative research to support the Net Zero transition, increasing awareness and active societal engagement, and leading by example.

In May 2022, the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities (ALLEA) released the report [“Towards Climate Sustainability of the Academic System in Europe and beyond”](#). By summarising data on the greenhouse gas emissions from various actors in the academic sector, the report highlights that the academic sector is currently not climate sustainable, and it is critical to take action. Through illustrations of good practices and concrete recommendations, the report offers actionable strategies to significantly reduce the annual greenhouse gas emissions generated by the academic sector. It prioritises deliberation, balance, and consideration of all relevant perspectives to enable an academic environment that promotes environmental sustainability without compromising research excellence or hindering international collaboration.

The current short report follows up on this previous work assessing the different approaches to Net Zero currently in place within European academies of sciences and humanities themselves. Based on a survey among ALLEA’s membership, it provides a qualitative overview of existing policies and initiatives, as well as a selection of established initiatives and recommendations that can directly be implemented by individual academies and umbrella organisations like ALLEA. This short report is intended to form a basis for the dissemination and promotion of good practices and further in-depth monitoring of the transition towards Net Zero within the European academies.

RECOMMENDATIONS TO EUROPEAN ACADEMIES

Based on the data received, recommendations to the European academies of sciences and humanities include to:

1. **formalise their commitment** to Net Zero by including this as a priority in their Statutes or Mission, and/or by signing a pledge to Net Zero, and publicly communicating this;
 2. **define their timeline and measures** towards becoming Net Zero (including intermediate goals), considering their unique challenges as well as national laws and regulations;
 3. **develop and implement internal policies** for sustainable travel, organising events, and other operations, and ensure they are aligned with national laws and regulations;
 4. **report on an annual basis** on their targets, progress, and activities towards Net Zero, while actively avoiding any instances of greenwashing or the perception thereof;
 5. **inform society to support a just and fair transition** towards Net Zero by promoting public awareness and active engagement and participating in relevant education programmes;
- provide science-based advice** for policymakers and other stakeholders, while recognising gaps and uncertainties and critically reflecting on carbon-offsetting as a tool for reaching Net Zero.

RECOMMENDATIONS TO ALLEA

In addition, European umbrella organisations like ALLEA are recommended to:

1. **continue to provide a platform** for ALLEA Member Academies to discuss their progress and challenges related to the above recommendations and promote sharing of innovative approaches to Net Zero and sustainability;
2. **leverage its position as convener in the academic system**, to bring together different stakeholder organisations to share good practices across the community.

STEERING GROUP

To oversee the collection and analysis of Net Zero data from among ALLEA's membership, a Steering Group was established, taking into consideration geography and gender balance, representation of senior and young academics, gender, and involving both academy fellows and senior-level staff members:

Name	Academy
Luke Drury (Steering Group co-chair)	ALLEA Vice President – Royal Irish Academy
Hugo Clarke (Steering Group co-chair)	British Academy
George Sakellaris	Czech Academy of Sciences
Margarita Popova	Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
Antonello Provenzale	Academy of Sciences of Torino
Soteris Kalogirou	Cyprus Academy of Sciences, Letters and Arts
Christos Zerefos	Academy of Athens
Astrid Eichhorn	German Young Academy
Síle Lane	Royal Irish Academy
Melle Jan Kromhout	Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences
Natalia Sobczak	Polish Academy of Sciences

NET ZERO RESPONSES FROM ALLEA MEMBER ACADEMIES

ALLEA Member Academies were invited to submit their current approaches to Net Zero, considering (but not limited to) the below categories:

- Existing policies and timelines to reach specific goals/outcomes
- Past and/or ongoing initiatives in your academy to support Net Zero
- Activities to promote awareness and change among fellowship and staff

The ALLEA Secretariat received 28 submissions from among its membership, including one notifying that no Net Zero approaches were in place.

Disclaimers to the data

- As many of the submissions contain internal policies and other confidential information, all data or recommendations are only presented or shared in an anonymised manner.
- To encourage the submission of a broad range of policies, recommendations, and actions, no specific information or formats were requested. As a result, it is at this stage not possible to draw any quantitative conclusions. For example, if an academy did not report any public engagement activities, this can simply mean that they did not consider it relevant to report in this context.
- Several academies emphasised that they are not fully autonomous in deciding which Net Zero approaches to pursue. Importantly, national laws and regulations may be in place that demand certain actions according to specific timelines, and similar demands can be placed by funders (often the national government). Also, academies are frequently located in protected historical buildings, which puts restraints on the type of energy-saving measures that can be implemented through reconstruction.

OVERVIEW OF ACADEMY APPROACHES TO NET ZERO

The below table provides an overview of the different types of approaches to Net Zero that have been identified among ALLEA's membership, grouped in five categories. Whereas some approaches have been reported by multiple academies, others may have only been reported once – rather than providing a quantitative overview of the status quo, this table therefore intends to provide a resource for academies who seek inspiration for further approaches towards Net Zero.

Policies & Guidelines
Formalising Net Zero as a priority in the academy's Statutes or Mission
Developing an approach towards Net Zero with clear targets and timelines
Creating internal guidelines for sustainable travel, events, energy use, etc.
Signalling the academy's commitment by signing or publishing a pledge to Net Zero
Reporting
Reporting approaches to Net Zero, for example as part of the academy's annual report
Establishing yearly energy efficiency / greenhouse gas emission reporting
Organisation
Appointing a Net Zero committee or delegate to lead the transition to Net Zero
Aiming for the organisation to achieve certification, such as ISO certification for energy management
Organising lectures and roundtables with staff to create awareness and a sense of shared responsibility

Establishing 'Green Teams' to promote awareness and lead on initiatives and implementation
Awards to recognise or stimulate ideas improving sustainability
Practical operations
Reducing use of plastics and promote waste separation and recycling
Reducing paper use by digitising paper-based processes and reducing printing
Changing to more sustainable energy sources and usage; monitoring and regulating energy use locally
Improving energy efficiency of buildings and operations
Promoting online or hybrid events
Mandating/incentivising more sustainable travel options
Selecting sustainable venues (or adopting measures to become one), catering, etc. for events
Research and funding activities
Funding research(ers) on topics related to sustainability, energy transition, etc.
Digitalising libraries, archives, publications, etc. to reduce travel and facilitate access to resources
Societal awareness & Policy advice
Organising public lectures and other events on sustainability to improve public awareness
Participating in public debates to represent the scholarly community
Creating educational activities for all ages, from primary school to PhD students and professionals
Organising and participate in solution-oriented fora with policymakers and other stakeholders
Publishing evidence-based reports and policy briefs on sustainability

RESOURCES OF ESTABLISHED INITIATIVES

The below overview comprises a selection of established initiatives identified within ALLEA's membership and is not intended to provide an exhaustive list of all measures taken at ALLEA Member Academies. Only publicly available resources are listed:

- The Royal Netherlands Academy of Arts and Sciences publishes an [Annual Sustainability Report](#), covering both its internal operations and research activities. Likewise, the Royal Society reports its commitment to Net Zero and specific actions as part of its [Annual Report](#).
- The Royal Irish Academy takes part in the yearly [Reporting of Energy Consumption](#) since 2009, the data of which are publicly available. The Academy of Athens is embracing solar and geothermal energy for its 130-year-old building to become Net Zero ([link](#)), and several academies are undergoing substantial reconstruction to become more energy efficient.
- The Young Academy of Scotland published a [Sustainable Business Travel Pledge](#), together with an [Air Travel Justification Tool](#). The Junge Akademie (German Young Academy) provides a list of [Practical Tips to Reduce Travel](#) on its website.
- The Swiss Academy of Sciences (SCNAT) has guidelines for [Organising Sustainable Events](#).
- The British Academy has a [Net Zero Governance Programme](#), which aims at producing practical policy outputs that explore how improving the quality of governance can contribute to achieving Net Zero.
- The Norwegian Academy of Science and Letters has a dedicated [Committee](#) on climate and environment that organises events and publishes statements to improve communication between the various disciplines and between science and the public.

- The 2022 [ALLEA Report Towards Climate Sustainability of the Academic System in Europe and beyond](#) provides recommendations on how academies can make their own operations climate-sustainable and provide a platform for discussion with different stakeholders. Based on these, ALLEA has adopted its own climate sustainability policies, covering internal meetings, public events, travelling and office procedures.

ABOUT ALLEA

ALLEA is the European Federation of Academies of Sciences and Humanities, representing nearly 60 academies from about 40 EU and non-EU countries. Since its foundation in 1994, ALLEA speaks out on behalf of its members on European and international stages, promotes science as a global public good, and facilitates scientific collaboration across borders and disciplines. Learn more here: www.allea.org.

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